

THE STUDY OF THE LEXICON OF MEASUREMENT BY LINGUISTS

Adxamova Shohina Anvarjon qizi
Ferghana State University

The Metrological dictionary is one of the ancient elements of the study of the linguistic picture of the world, the study of which is the main issue in the field of linguistic and humanitarian knowledge in general. Analysis of the characteristics of this dictionary allows us to reveal the systematic potential of language tools, to identify their intra-and inter-group lexical relationships.

With the beginning of the second half of the twentieth century, the studies of linguists gave rise to the idea of the need to study the lexical composition of a metrological dictionary.

Romanova G.Y. argues that the trends in the development of the lexical system can be explained only taking into account the historical conditions in which the life of the human community continued [Romanova, 1972. 7]. As historians have noted, in Metrological practice, volume measurements were distinguished by two specific areas of application: for dry objects and liquids - and this was typical of all peoples [Shostin, 1975. P .29]. Currently, modern science is forming a classification of measures that slightly differ in size from each other.

V. V. According to Vinogradov, " the history of production, lifestyle, culture, science, technology, the history of the social worldview are closely and very organically related to the history of the dictionary... The relationship of the history of the language with the history of social development is directly and comprehensively determined" [Vinogradov V. V. 1977, 70].

Similarly meaningful statement B. A. belonging to Larin: "the vocabulary of language is directly and broadly related to the history of people, their views, moral assessments, social structure, lifestyle and cultural achievements. This position is based on the long and rich experience of linguists " [larin, 1977,46].

At the end of the 18th century, the Scottish engineer J. Watt introduced the term "horsepower" to define horsepower. With this name, Watt wanted to show how many horses could replace the work of the steam engines he invented. At the end of the 19th century, a new unit of power measurement was introduced—a Watt named after the inventor. Since then, the term "horsepower" has ceased to be officially used, though it is still used to calculate the transport tax in many countries. The source of measurement was parts of the human body, just as fingers and toes were (and sometimes still are) used in counting.

G. Y. Romanov, V. V. Lebedinskaya's linguistic work has historically had a more generalizing nature of describing length measures. [Lebedinskaya, 2000,169,], but they are devoted to the description of individual groups of the Metrological dictionary. G. ya. According to Romanov, all measurements of volume (capacity) include: measurements for loose bodies and for liquid and dense bodies. according to the author, these were "two properly structured systems with distinctive features depend on the region".

To fully reveal many unknown aspects of this problem, it is necessary to study historical Metrology in parallel in the works of modern historians, archaeologists and other scientists, where it is very important to analyze the names on historical metrology carried out by linguists.

V. V. As Shevtsov noted, using linguistic analysis of Metrological names, it is possible to determine their origin (the name of the measure can be associated with local economic practice or be the result of mastering from other languages for political or economic reasons), "it is necessary to determine the methods of measurement, the composition of the group of measures, the time of their appearance and the

M. The classification compiled by Mladentsev should of course be noted I, in which there are four: "measures of length, measures of area, measures of weight, measures of volume" gruppas[Mladentsev, 1907, 180] this classification most accurately reflects the evolution of the lexical category of measurement in sources of different historical periods, therefore, when describing Metrological names in this study, M. The classification proposed by Mladentsev was taken as a basis.

Analysis of the scientific literature shows that it is most optimal to divide the Metrological dictionary into the following bases: names of linear measurements, field measurements, volume measurements and weight measurements. In comparison, the modern international metric system uses the term "weight measurement" instead of the term "mass measurement". In the international metric system, volumes are measured in cubic units (cubic letters, etc).

From the second half of the twentieth century, a new era begins in the study of Metrological vocabulary-during this period, works of linguists appear that affect the Metrological dictionary to varying degrees, in which various sources are used to study metrology and metrological terminology: both subject (material) and written monuments contain various information about measures. It should be noted that in both cases we are dealing with the linguistic expression of Metrological

Bibliography

THE ORIGINS OF MEASUREMENT & THE HISTORY OF MEASUREMENT SYSTEMS

2. M.E. Himbert A brief history of measurement (2009)
3. Davidovich, E.A. Material po metrologii srednevekovoy Sredney Azii / e.A. Davidovich. - M.: Nauka, 1970. - 147 P.
4. Danilenko, V.P. Linguistichesky aspekt standardizatsii terminologiy / V.P. Danilenko. - M., 1993.- 280 P.
5. Danilenko, V.P. Russkaya terminology: Opit lingvisticheskogo opisania / V.P. Danilenko. - M.: Nauka, 1977. - S79.
6. Danilenko, V.P. Terminology I norm. / V.P. Danilenko. - M.: Nauka, 1972.